

Comparison of Pashto and Dari Noun Cases

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Accepted Jan 21, 2021

Published Jan 26, 2021

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DOI :<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4468199>

Pages: 191-199

Funding: N/A

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How to cite this article (APA):

Ahmadullah kargar (2021).

Comparison of Pashto and Dari

Noun Cases. *North American*

Academic Research, 4(1), 191-

199. doi:<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4468199>

[zenodo.4468199](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4468199)

Conflicts of Interest

There are no conflicts to declare.

ABSTRACT

Comparison of Pashto and Dari noun cases is syntactical issue which is just belong to Pashto and Dari official languages of Afghanistan. The study used qualitative descriptive method to find out similarities and difference in noun cases of Pashto and Dari languages. The result of this study showed that both languages has differences in noun cases. In addition, the result also elucidated that in Pashto language nominative, vocative and little bit accusative case are alive which are real oblique cases and the other cases are appearing by the support of some preposition and postposition. On the other hand, without vocative case, Dari language also appear noun cases by the aid of some preposition and postposition.

Keywords: Case marks, Direct form, Noun case, Oblique form

Introduction

Pashto and Dari are Members of Indo-European language family, which are belong to Indo-Aryan branch and Aryan Group. Both are official languages of Afghanistan and are spoken in different geographical areas, thus, all Afghans have to acquire both languages (Dari, and Pashto) in educational and formal places. Deliberately, there are some grammatical differences which should be brought under consideration during learning Pashto and Dari languages. In addition, Pashto and Dari languages have differences and similarities including noun causes. Therefore, these differences and similarities have made it difficult for Pashtuns to learn Dari and vice versa. Furthermore, we detect the historical evolution of these languages. Consequently, this study covered a small part of grammar of both languages.

Ancient Aryan languages have specific marks for noun cases, which can be added at the end of the

noun to determine the cases from them, such as the nominative, dative, possessive and etc. (Darmesteter et al 1997, 113-114) explained that Pashto and Dari languages do not retain completely these ancient marks, instead of these marks, they used some preposition and postposition in both languages. In addition, the last period of the old Persian was so perplexing in noun cases. suffixes, that one can only explicate the disappearance of the cases. Aftermath, in Middle and new Persian the system is completely destroy (Dost 2014, 314). In addition to as a novelty of this study in the past tense of Pashto, the transitive verb subject uses in oblique form and in Dari language subject always uses in direct form. in vocative case always come in indirect or oblique form while in Dari language except of some nouns which take /ā/ all occur in direct form. Without two Pashto pronouns (/mā – ما/ and /tā – تا/) both languages have lost the accusative case and both languages express instrumental case with the help of preposition.

Likewise, (Darmesteter et al 1997, 113-114) has researched on the comparison of Pashto and Dari noun cases. The research has not covered the whole issue, because it has only enlightened possessive, dative, ablative, and locative case. In this regard, (Mehdi 2011, 45-46) has also mentioned these four cases but Nominative, Vocative, Accusative and Instrumental cases are not compared and also there were limited researches to show the noun cases comparison in Pashto and Dari languages therefore this study was conducted to find out the similarities and differences in nouns cases of Pashto and Dari languages.

Materials and methods

This research carried out based on the library (qualitative descriptive) method. Furthermore, many books have been studied by the researcher to find out comparison of noun cases in Pashto and Dari language and as a result, only two books were selected which discussed this issue. In addition, the researcher collected grammars books of both languages from different libraries and selected books that had academic validity and link to this study.

1. Nominative case

Except from a few non-oblique nouns in the Pashto language, all the other nouns take different forms during the Nominative case. The Pashto nominative case just belong to past transitive verb subject (Khwishkay 2009, 50).

Examples:

[sarī ɖoɖay xwará]	سړي ډوډۍ خوړه.	Man was eating bread.
[zarmine maqāla likalá]	زرميني مقاله ليكله.	Zarmina was writing essay.
[zalmi kār kāwə]	زلمي کار کاوه.	Zalmay was working.

In the above sentences, the nouns [saray, zarmina, zalmay] come in the form of [sarī, zarmine, zalmij] which has a specific ending. If the noun ending in an /ay – ۍ/ Diphthong, take on /i – ې/ ending in Nominative case. and the nouns ending in /a – // take on /e – ې/. Which are called Nominative

case marks. In support, Dr. Mojawar Ahmad Zyar illuminated that this case is the real Pashto oblique case (Zyar 2005, 93). On the other hand, Dari language have lost the marks of Nominative cases and there is no noun in the nominative case, that has given the same marks as the above marks. if we translate the above Pashto sentences into Dari, there are no marks of nominative case.

[<i>mard nān mexurd</i>]	مرد نان میخورد.	Man was eating bread.
[<i>zarmina maqāla menawišt</i>]	زرمینه مقاله مینویشته.	zarmina was writing essay.
[<i>zalmay kār mekard</i>]	زلمی کار میکرد.	zalmay was working

2. Vocative case

In the Pashto language, vocative case is a little more alive than the eight ancient Indo-European noun cases which is called the real oblique noun case and each noun take on a specific ending, such as /a/ and /e/ ending.

[<i>(ya) halaka!</i>]	(به) هلکه!	Boy!
[<i>(ya) wrora!</i>]	(به) وروره!	Brother!
[<i>(ya) xore!</i>]	(به) خورې!	Sister!
[<i>(ya) zalmaya!</i>]	(به) زلمیه!	Zalmay!

In Dari, there is the vocative case mark /ā – ī/, which is added at the end of the noun. If the noun ends in /ā – ī/ or /w – و/, So the /y – ی/ is preceded by vocative mark (ā – ī) and becomes an allomorph, Examples:

[<i>xudāyā!</i>]	خدایا!	God!
[<i>pisarā!</i>]	پسرا!	Son!
[<i>yārā!</i>]	یارا!	Darling!

Sometimes /āy – ای/ or /āyā – یا/ comes before noun, such as: [*āy xudāyā!*], [*āy pisarā!*], [*āy yārā!*] (Qarib et al. 2015, 44; Majid 2018, 40). If Dari nouns occur direct form in the vocative case, the stress occurs at first syllable (Elham 2012, 109).

Some examples:

[<i>zālmay!</i>]	زلمی!	Zalmay!
[<i>āhmad!</i>]	احمد!	Ahmad!
[<i>bāča!</i>]	بچه!	Boy!

3. Dative case

In Pashto language, dative case is real oblique case because if each noun has oblique form take on specific changeable ending and followed by the /ta – ته/ postposition, it means /ta – ته/ comes after a noun which is used in dative case. Examples:

[<i>ahmad malgəri ta ketāb warkər</i>]	احمد ملگري ته کتاب ورکړ.	Ahmad handed the book to friend.
[<i>jamile zarmine ta qalam wāxist</i>]	جمیلې زرمینې ته قلم واخیست.	Jamila has bought pen to Zarmina.
[<i>jamila najibe ta qalam āxli</i>]	جمیله تجیبې ته قلم اخلی.	Jamila is buying pen to Najiba.

In these sentences, the nouns [malgəri], [zarmine] and [najibe] have dative cases. The first noun Take on /-i - ي / and the last two /-e - ي / . On the other hand, Dari language lost the dative case marks and its job is performing by some preposition, such as: /ba – به /, /barāye – برای /, bā – با ... / for example:

[ahmad ketāb rā ba andiwāl dād] احمد کتاب را به اندیوال داد. Ahmad handed the book to friend.
 [jamila qalam rā ba zarmina xarid] جمیله قلم را به زرمینه خرید. Jamila has bought pen to Zarmina.
 [jamila qalam rā ba zarmina mexarid] جمیله قلم را به زرمینه میخرد. Jamila buys pen to zarmina.

I would also like to mention, that the /rā – را / is also used before the indirect object and /ba - به / preposition which are called Dari dative case mark. Comparatively, it can be understood that after the Pashto indirect object comes /ta - ته /, sometime /la - له / and /lara - لره / is also used instead of /ta - ته /, which belong to spoken Pashto language. Moreover, each singular, plural, masculine and feminine nouns are uses instead of indirect object or uses in dative case, but some of them have oblique form and take on a specific oblique form mark like above mentioned nouns. on the other hand, Dari nouns has not had oblique form and uses direct form of nouns in dative case. If we look at the background of Pashto dative case, it can be noticed that Pashto dative case has the following forms:

/wə/+noun+/ta/ = [wə saʁi ta]	وسري ته	To man
/wə/+noun+/wə ta/ = [wə saʁi wə ta]	وسري وته	To man
noun+/wə ta/ = [saʁi wə ta]	سري وته	To man
noun+/ta/ = [saʁi ta]	سري ته	To man
noun+/lara/ = [saʁi lara]	سري لره	To man
noun+/la/ = [saʁi la]	سري له	To man

This /w – و / in Pashto which precedes the noun, may have its root in Avesta words and used to indicate direction. Mr. Morgenstern explored that /ta – ته / is the etymologically a remnant of [apari-šta] and Probably, [šta] is the root of /ta – ته /, /ta – ته / which also existed in Dari. First was /tāk – تاک / and then /tā – تا /.

/lara – لره / is also used in some Pashto dialects after indirect object instead of /ta – ته /. According to Morgenstern, the origin of /lar – لر / was probably the avesta [rād] which is the origin of /rāy, rā/ in Dari.

Likewise, /la – له / is used after indirect object instead of /ta – ته /, Some Linguist think that /la – له / is an abbreviated form of /lara – لره /. Similarly, meaning /r – ر / is omitted and /la – له / made of it but Darmesteter 1997, 112 claimed that it derived from the avestian [da].

4. Accusative case

Zyar 2005, 93 explicated that real oblique accusative case is very rarely active in Pashto language

and it just come with first person singular oblique pronoun /*mā* - ما/ and second person singular oblique pronoun /*tā* - تا/ in present tense Such as:

[*tə mā wine*] ته ما وينې you see me.
 [*zə tā winəm*] زه تا وينم I see you.

In above sentences the personal pronouns (/mā – ما/ and /tā – تا/) occur in accusative cases and both pronoun used in oblique form. Besides, these two pronouns, all Pashto nouns and pronouns are used in direct form. For examples:

[*jamila zarmina wini*] جميله زرمينه وينې. Jamila sees Zarmina.
 [*jamile zarmina lida*] جميلې زرمينه لیده. Jamila was seeing Zarmina.

Similarly, like the Pashto language, Dari has also lost accusative case marks. like:

[*jamila zarmina rā mebinad*] جميله زرمينه را می بیند. Jamila sees Zarmina.
 [*jamila zarmina rā did*] جميله زرمينه را دید. Jamila was seeing Zarmina.

In the above Dari language sentences, the noun /*zarmina* – زرمينه/ has accusative case which is followed by /*rā* – را/ postposition and /*rā* – را/ postposition is the grammatical symbol of the accusative case in Dari. If /*rā* – را/ postposition is not use between direct object and verb, the compound objects with verb will be changed to compound verb or verbal phrase (Sharifi 2016, 133).

5. Instrumental case

Pashto language executes instrumental case with the help of /*pə* - په/ preposition.

[*hayə pə qalam lik likə*] هغه په قلم ليک ليکه. He was writing letter by pen.
 [*ahmad pə largy haya wāhə*] احمد په لرگي هغه واهه. Ahmad was hitting him by stick.

If /*sara* – سره/ postposition come together with /*pə* - په/ preposition, so, all /*a*/ended nouns, take on /*e* - ي/ sound in instrumental case which is oblique form of these nouns (Zyar 2005, 94; Khwishkay 2016, 132). e.g.

[*haya pə kāšuyə sara ɖoɖəy xuri*] هغه په کاشوغي سره ډوډی خوري. He eats meal by spoon.
 [*hayə pə tiğə sara zə wəwištəm*] هغه په تیري سره زه وويشتم. He hit me by stone.

Comparing, Dari language uses /*ba* – به/ as an Equivalent to Pashto /*pə* - په/ for instrumental case, like:

[*u ba qalam xat nawišt*] او به قلم خط نویشته. He was writing letter by pen.

In addition, some other morphemes (/hamrā/, /tawasut/) are also used for instrumental case in Dari language. Notably, some Dari language speaker and author combine the below two kind of morphemes for deriving instrumental case. such as in below second sentence:

[*u tawasut e qalam xat nawišt*] او توسط قلم خط نویشته. He was writing letter by pen.
 [*u ba wasila e qalam xat nawišt*] او به وسیله قلم خط نویشته. He was writing letter by pen.

6. Possessive case

The Pashto language uses /d – د/ particle for possessive case. like in these phrases:

[de jamile wror]	د جمیلې وروړ	Jamila's brother
[de ahmad ketāb]	د احمد کتاب	Ahmad's book

In above phrases “Jamila” and “Ahmad” nouns have possessive cases and each one preceded by /de – د/ possessive particle. All Pashto nouns are come in oblique form if the nouns have oblique form in possessive case.

The structure of Pashto possessive phrase is that first comes possessive particle then possessor and at the end of this phrase come possessed. If possessor is weak personal pronouns, so possessed comes before possessor and possessive particle (de – د) is omitted. As well as, if possessor is /zamā – زما/ and /stā – ستا/ possessive pronouns, the possessive particle omitted. Like as below:

[wror me], [wror de], [wror ye]	ورور مې، وروړ دې، وروړ بې	My brother, Your brother, His/her brother.
[zamā wror], [stā wror]	زما وروړ، ستا وروړ	My brother, Your brother.

There is major difference between the Western and Eastern Aryan languages regarding the structure of possessive phrase. In Eastern Aryan languages, first noun of the possessive phrase functioning as the possessive case while in western Aryan languages second noun functioning as possessive case. The possessive phrase structure of the Dari language is similar to the Western Aryan languages, such as the nouns or pronouns /mā – ما/, "Zarmina", and "Zmaray" in these phrases.

[xāna yi mā]	خانه ی ما	My house
[ketāb i zarmina]	کتاب زرمینه	Zarmina's book
[qalam i zmaray]	قلم زمری	Zmaray's pen

In above phrases, /i/ is Dari language possessive morpheme and /yi/ is allomorph of this morpheme. /i/ comes after the nouns which are ending by consonant and /yi/ comes after vowel ending nouns (Elham 2012, 108; yamen 2014, 83). In summary, the Dari language possessed is occur after possessor and the possessive marks occur between the two nouns while in Pashto language, first comes possessive morpheme then the possessor and finally possessed. The possessor noun of both languages has possessive case and the Pashto possessive case get oblique form of nouns while the Dari language has direct form. According to Darmesteter, the Pashto possessive morpheme (de – د) is derivate from the avesta "hača", but Muller and Geiger explicate that it is derivate from Old Persian "tya" (Darmesteter 1997, 113).

7. Ablative case

Pashto ablative case is articulated with the support of /ə - له/ preposition. The below examples

revealed that noun (/pohantun – پوهنتون/) has ablative case. In addition, it also creates an adverb of place with and /caxa – څخه/ postposition which are illuminated in the second example (Zyar, 2005, 94).

[zə lə pohantuna rāyləm]	زه له پوهنتونه راغلم.	I come from university.
[zə lə pohantun caxa rāyləm]	زه له پوهنتون څخه راغلم.	I come from university.

Comparing to Pashto language, most of Dari grammars, the ablative case performed complementary role (Ishraqi 2015, 254). It should be noted that only the ablative case is not limited to complementary role but also locative case and instrumental case also come under this heading. whereas Dari language derived ablative case with the help of /az – از/ preposition and we can find nouns (“pohantun” and “daftar”) ablative case in these example:

[man az pohantun āmadəm]	من از پوهنتون امدم.	I come from university.
[omid az daftar ba xāna rapt]	امید از دفتر به خانه رفت.	Omid went home from the office.

As a result, the Pashto language uses /lə – له/ preposition for ablative case and Dari languages uses /az – از/ preposition (Mehdi, 2011, 46). Moreover, both languages prepositions come before the nouns which occur in ablative cases that are articulated in the above Pashto and Dari examples. The Pashto /lə/ preposition which is used for the ablative case can be used alone and it should be paired with postposition (/caxa/ or /na/) to get ablative case. Furthermore, each noun takes a special ending if the noun has oblique form and take just /a/, if the noun is not mutable and end by a consonant. In the above Pashto examples, it is known that in ancient Aryan languages, the ablative case was Explained by changing the last phoneme of the noun. Notably, in Dari language nouns have not oblique form in ablative case thus they are always use in direct form.

8. Locative case

Zyar (2005, 94) elaborated that Pashto language derived locative case with the aid of some preposition and postposition like: /pə - ke/, /pər – bānde/, /pər – barsera/, /tər – lānde/, /tər – pore/ while Dari language derived this case by the support of two prepositions which are /dar – در/, and /bar – بر/.

Pashto examples:

[pə koʃa ke]	په کوټه کې	in the room.
[pər mez bande]	پر میز باندې	on the table.
[pər mez barsera]	پر میز برسېره	on the table
[tər mez lānde]	تر میز لاندې	under the table.

It can Omits postposition in second and third examples.

Dari examples:

[dar otāq]	در اتاق	in the room.
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Conclusion

In summary, past tense of Pashto language, the transitive verb subject uses in oblique form which is real oblique nominative case but in Dari language subject always uses in direct form. Additionally, conjugated nouns of Pashto, in vocative case always come in indirect or oblique form while in Dari language except of some nouns which take /ā/ all occur in direct form. The traces of the accusative case appear in Pashto only in the oblique pronouns /mā – ما / and /tā – تا /, except of these two pronouns in Pashto both languages have lost the accusative case. Pashto Instrumental case expresses with the help of /pə - په / and Dari with the help of /ba – به /.

Likewise, the Dative case of Pashto is conjugate and /ta – ته / postposition also comes after the noun. Notably, all nouns in Dari language appear in direct form. As well as /ta – ته / postposition is the Pashto language dative case and /rā – را / is in Dari language. Notably, Pashto nouns little bit conjugated and Dari are not. Deliberately, in the possessive and ablative case of Pashto language nouns are conjugated while in Dari language is null. As a final point, both languages have lost the locative case (marks).

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